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Multi-Point Activity Surveys: A novel technique for the analysis of the movements of Daubenton's bat *Myotis daubentonii* (Kuhl, 1817) on Waterways

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Background

Landscape-scale data on bat movements are often gained through radio tagging and telemetry, which can provide information on roost locations, nightly movements and commuting routes (Collins, 2016). Whilst effective and accurate, these methods have several disadvantages. The cost of equipment for radio telemetry may be prohibitively expensive; the availability of skilled and appropriately licensed surveyors may be limited (Hughes *et al.*, 2021); and access to private land to track bat movements may be difficult to obtain (Hourigan *et al.*, 2008). Additionally (and partially as a result of resource limitations), the number of individual bats from which meaningful data can be gained in a single study is often low. We sought to develop a robust, repeatable and cost-effective method for monitoring the movements of multiple bats at a landscape scale. To that end, we have developed the Multi-Point Activity Survey (MultiPAS) technique, which requires minimal field training and equipment, is focused on publicly accessible land, and can be undertaken under a Class 1 bat licence. The technique focuses on waterways which, in the case of our pilot study, was a network of urban canals north of Birmingham.

Daubenton's bat *Myotis daubentonii* has a documented affinity for water (Altringham, 2003), with their roosts generally being found within 200m of lentic and riparian habitats (Ngamprasertwong *et al.*, 2014). Though they are known to be encountered readily in woodlands, they utilise linear features (Dietz and Kiefer, 2014) such as waterways to commute nightly from their roosts, emerging and flying directly to their preferred feeding areas, with each bat showing high fidelity to one or two foraging sites (Altringham, 2003; Rainho and Palmeirim, 2011) which are usually within 3km of the roost (Altringham, 2003). The MultiPAS method combines acoustic monitoring with visual observations of bat passes along waterways, and is based upon the fact that Daubenton's bat is known to commute almost exclusively within 1m above water's surface (Altringham, 2003) with an average of 15.8cm above the surface (Kalko and Schnitzler, 1989). This predictability affords surveyors the opportunity to use torches to aid in visual observations of individual bats as they undertake their commuting flight.

We have developed and field tested the MultiPAS method and used it effectively to gather data on multiple individual bats (in our case, up to 80 individuals per survey) to determine main commuting routes, key hop-on and hop-off points and important crossing points (authors' own unpublished data). The applications for the data are diverse, and include population monitoring, assessing potential impacts for developments along waterways, establishing mitigation effectiveness where watercourses are changed, identifying bat commuting routes and suggesting candidate sites for the establishment of dark corridors.

The MultiPAS method can be used as an alternative to invasive and prohibitively expensive methods of radio tagging and tracking and can provide large datasets of robust, quantitative data on a landscape scale in a repeatable manner, on multiple bats in a single survey. It can be carried out with minimal field training using readily available materials. Further applications have also been demonstrated to be effective for roost counts at tunnels, and activity surveys at barriers, aqueducts and bridges. Here, we present two main models for MultiPAS and several supplementary applications.

Survey Design

General methods

The fundamental survey design for the study is that of teams (usually four) of surveyors being positioned at set intervals **Error! Reference source not found.** along sections of a waterway (Figure 1). Utilising a combination of acoustic monitoring and visual observations, the movements of individual Daubenton’s bats are tracked as they commute from their day roosts to their foraging areas. Equipment comprising bat detectors and red LED torches is positioned facing the opposite bank. Upon observing each bat passing a survey point, the survey team at that position use two-way radios to give verbal cues to alert adjacent teams to anticipate the ingress/pass of a bat.

Figure 1: Indicative positioning and spacing of survey teams and equipment for MultiPAS. Icons used with permission from Microsoft Office 365.

Timings

The MultiPAS method was developed with the aim of observing, recording and analysing the movements of Daubenton’s bat with a focus on commuting movements at emergence only. To that end, the survey timings were designed accordingly. Daubenton’s bat is reported to have mean emergence times ranging (in minutes after sunset) from 28 ± 12 minutes to 105 ± 15 minutes (Swift and Racey, 1983; Jones and Rydell, 1994; Warren *et al.*, 2000; Altringham, 2003; Lucan, 2009). The species has also been documented to have mean emergence times on average of 14 minutes earlier during the post-parturition period (Lucan, 2009), an observation borne out in the recent work by Annette Faulkner (2022) who recorded emergence at sunset ± 40 minutes in June, but sunset +20 post-parturition. The species-specific protocols developed for monitoring Daubenton’s bat of the National Bat Monitoring Programme’s Waterways Survey (Bat Conservation Trust, 2020) comprise a start time of sunset +40 mins after sunset and a duration of 60 minutes. For MultiPAS surveys, this timing was altered to accommodate the anticipated earlier emergence of the post-

parturition period, with **surveys commencing at sunset +30 minutes and lasting for 60 minutes**. We would recommend adopting standard activity survey effort with regard to number of visits per season/month as per the Surveys for Professional Ecologists: Good Practice Guidelines (Collins, 2016).

Equipment

Key pieces of field equipment to undertake MultiPAS surveys are as follows: each team should have a bat detector – heterodyne is adequate, however we recommend a live-view, full spectrum unit such as the Wildlife Acoustics EchoMeter Touch 2 Pro (with auto-ID turned off so that popups do not obscure the display). Each team also requires a red LED torch¹ and a two-way radio with which to communicate with other teams.

Field Identification

For our pilot studies, auto-identification on the EchoMeter Touch 2 Pro detectors (Wildlife Acoustics Inc., 2018) was disabled due to the display being obscured during notifications. As the most commonly encountered species (Daubenton's bat, noctule *Nyctalus noctula*, common pipistrelle *Pipistrellus pipistrellus*, and soprano pipistrelle *P. pygmaeus*) are all readily identifiable by their distinct sonograms (Hughes *et al.*, 2020) with moderate field training, surveyors were able to accurately separate these species from other bats. The calls of Daubenton's bat comprise a largely frequency modulated structure, giving a 'dry' call which is in contrast to those of other common species (e.g. *Pipistrellus* and *Nyctalus*). Calls sweep from a mean of 81.1kHz to a mean of 29.4kHz, with a peak frequency of 41.8 – 56.5kHz (mean 47.0kHz). The calls also exhibit a qCF component mid-call (Russ, 2013), lending the pulses a sigmoidal profile (Newson and Berthinussen, 2019). In addition, the habit of this species of flying immediately above water creates distinctive missing frequencies (Russ, 2013), often called 'comb filtering'. This, coupled with visual observations of medium-sized bats flying low over the water affords surveyors confidence in field identifications with only a moderate amount of field training.

Survey Models

Prior to survey work, daytime reconnaissance surveys and aerial mapping should be used to plan survey locations for both models presented below. This should include safety considerations such as access, walking routes and parking.

Model 1: Linear Model

The aims of the Linear Survey Model were to identify 'hop on' and 'hop off' points used by bats along the waterways, inferring commuting routes to foraging grounds. In our study we used 16 locations approximately 200m apart² (named Alpha to Papa) covering a 3km section

¹ In our initial field testing, we recorded multiple incidences of light aversion when using white torches for the survey method, with some individual bats turning back along their route. We have not made any observations of avoidance behaviour when using red LED torches, and so for welfare (as well as survey efficacy) reasons, would not recommend using white lights for the MultiPAS method.

² The number of survey locations in the study area should be divisible by the approximate number of teams available. At our spacing and in a relatively flat landscape, four teams at 200m intervals can all hear each other on two-way radios, but greater spacing and a greater number of survey teams may alter radio efficacy.

of canal (Figure 2). Each survey covered four survey points with subsequent visits ‘moving up’ the line of the points and overlapping the previous survey’s end point (e.g. survey 1 – Alpha to Delta; survey 2 – Delta to Golf, etc.), covering the whole survey area in five survey visits and providing survey coverage with no gaps between survey points.

Figure 2: Linear survey model Pilot Study survey points, spacing at approximately 200m.

Figure 3: Indicative positioning of surveyors and equipment for MultiPAS Linear survey model. Icons used with permission from Microsoft Office 365.

At each survey point, equipment was deployed with LED torch positioned with the beam illuminating the opposite bank and bat detectors also facing the opposite bank (Figure 3). Teams watched the beam for passing bats and upon each bat pass, used their two-way radio to alert the other teams of the bat’s position and direction of travel (e.g. ‘Alpha, bat north’). This alerted the adjacent team in the direction of travel to anticipate a bat pass in a set

amount of time³ based on the distance between survey points. For each bat pass data recording comprised time, first and last contact points, and direction of travel.

Model 2: Junctions Model

The aims of the Junctions Survey Model were to identify commuting routes at canal junctions. The surveys comprised three teams (Alpha, Bravo and Charlie) positioned 125m from the canal junction with the fourth team (Zulu) from the centre of the junction to provide information on movements from that vantage point (Figure 4). Observation and recording method is the same as for the Linear Survey Model, with the exception that direction of travel is recorded as ‘in’ or ‘out’ (of the junction). We also placed additional torches across each arm of the junction at Zulu survey point to assist in visual observations.

Figure 4: Indicative positioning of surveyors and equipment for MultiPAS Junctions survey model. Icons used with permission from Microsoft Office 365.

Data Interpretation

Interpretation of MultiPAS results is essentially based on ‘gaps’ in data. For example, multiple bat passes from Alpha to Bravo, but not reaching Charlie, would indicate a ‘hop off’ point between Bravo and Charlie; similarly a lack of passes at Alpha, but starting at Bravo and going through to Delta indicate a ‘hop on’ point between Alpha and Bravo. Identified (or likely) routes can then be inferred using aerial imagery to look at likely foraging grounds. An example of this from our pilot study is shown in Figure 5. This can then be substantiated by further crossing point-style, ideally with Night Vision Aids to confirm bat flight routes. Data (flight routes) can also be mapped over open source light pollution data (e.g. NASA, 2021) to provide contextual environmental information.

³ We undertook surveys timing bats along several waterways (straight and curved) in order to estimate transit time between survey points. Speeds ranged from 3.2 mps to 8.3 mps with a median of 5.9mps and a mean of 6.1mps (Figure 6.21) which gives an anticipated 200m transit time of ±32 seconds. This is in line with RHIDDS results which ranged from 2.8mps to 8.3mps with an average speed of 5.3mps (Middleton, 2006).

Figure 5: Routes taken by bats at pilot study site, with green arrows showing identified ‘hop-on’ points and red arrows showing ‘hop-off’ points and egress routes. Numbers denote mean percentage of bats using each route section during section surveys.

Further Applications

The MultiPAS method principles (i.e. a combined utilisation of visual and acoustic observations aided by bat detectors and red LED torches based on multiple simultaneous survey points) were used to undertake further investigations of the behaviour of commuting bats in the urban landscape, comprising:

Assessment of behaviour at barriers

We used the MultiPAS method to record the behaviour of Daubenton’s bat at structures which were deemed to have the potential to represent a barrier to commuting bats (e.g. motorways or major roads) where they were crossed by canals (e.g. via underpasses and aqueducts). Bats were recorded passing through or over structures (Figure 6) and any deviation from routes were recorded. Each bat’s transit was recorded as either ‘through’ (passing through the structure entirely), ‘over’ (continuing along canal but crossing over the road/barrier) or ‘turn’ (turning upon approaching the barrier; not crossing or passing through).

Figure 6: Diagram of surveyor positioning for road barriers survey method. Icons used with permission from Microsoft Office 365.

Assessment of behaviour at tunnels

The method for surveying canal tunnels uses the general principles of MultiPAS (torch, observation and anticipated timings). Both sides of a tunnel were surveyed simultaneously (Figure 7). Data allowed surveyors to infer commuting numbers in each direction, as well as the number of tenant (roosting) bats within each structure (total number of bats exiting the tunnel before any entered, plus (after first ingress) total bats minus total bats in).

Figure 7: Diagram of surveyor positioning for tunnels survey method. Icons used with permission from Microsoft Office 365.

Constraints and Considerations

Behaviour at locks

We undertook surveys at canal locks in order to assess the suitability of MultiPAS surveys in the vicinity of locks. Specifically, the aim was to assess how far away from a lock survey teams need to be positioned in order to have confidence in bats flying through the surface-level (defined as the area up to 75cm above the water's surface) torch beams, making the MultiPAS method viable. We determined that the distance from the bottom lock at which bats returned to 'cruising altitude' (i.e., were visible in torches) ranged from 20m to 100m, with a mean of 35.69m and a median of 25m. The point at which 95% of bat passes were captured by the MultiPAS technique was 70m from the lock.

Floating plants

We made a number of ad-hoc observations that surveys where there was an abundance of floating vegetation (particularly floating water fern *Azolla filiculoides*) in the centre of the channel, Daubenton's bats abandoned their normal flight routes and instead flew along the adjacent hedgerows, adding a constraint to survey efficacy.

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